

Modified ninhydrin spray reagent for the identification of amino acids on TLC plates[†]

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Abstract : Detection of amino acids has utmost importance for the evaluation of protein structure and also for the determination of the C-terminal units of degraded proteins. TLC is an important tool for the identification of amino acids by various specific and non-specific spray reagents. Among the reagents used, ninhydrin is the most popular because of its remarkably high sensitivity. However, ninhydrin produces the same purple/violet color with all amino acids except proline and hydroxyproline (which produce yellow color). An attempt has been made to resolve this color problem by using modified ninhydrin reagent (2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde), which is capable of developing various distinguishable stable colors with many amino acids on TLC plates with high sensitivities (0.01–0.80 µg). The important finding is that the reagent itself produces yellow color with most of the amino acids. The color pictures of the chromatograms by Digital Camera are also included to demonstrate the different colors. A probable mechanism for such color formation has also been proposed.

Keywords : Thin layer chromatography, amino acids, 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, ninhydrin.

Introduction

Amino acids are the building units of proteins. Identification of amino acids is extremely important for the evaluation of protein structure and also for the determination of the presence of amino acids in various natural products. There are several methods for the determination of amino acids in biological and pharmaceutical samples. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) finds its place when the relatively costly equipment required by other methods is unavailable. Again, it is an inexpensive method and consumes only small amounts of samples and solvents. Various stationary phases are available, although silica gel is by far the most widely used. Different mobile phases are also reported for chromatogram development. TLC is widely used for identification of amino acids by various spray reagents¹⁻⁵. Among these ninhydrin is the most popular because of its high sensitivity⁶. However, ninhydrin produces the same purple/violet color with most amino acids (only proline and hydroxyproline produces yellow color).

An attempt has been made to resolve this color problem by using modified ninhydrin reagent. A new modified ninhydrin spray reagent (2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde), with high sensitivities (0.01–0.80 µg) for easy and rapid identification of amino acids on thin layer chromatograms has been introduced. This reagent is capable of developing various distinguishable stable colors with many amino acids on TLC plates. The sensitivities are comparable to other reagents so far introduced¹⁻⁵ and more sensitive in many occasions than some other reagents³⁻⁵. Again, formation of yellow color (without use of ninhydrin) of almost all amino acids on TLC plates with 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, is an added advantage of this method. A probable mechanism for such color formation has also been proposed.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Chromatography plates (20 × 20 cm; thickness 0.1

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mm) were prepared with silica gel G (Merck, India) using Unoplan Coating apparatus (Shandon, London, UK). Photographs of the colored chromatograms were performed by Digital Camera (Nikon Coolpix L-25, China).

Reagents :

Ninhydrin and standard amino acids were obtained from Sigma (USA), *n*-propanol from Merck (India), 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (A.R.) was obtained from Fluka AG, Switzerland.

Reagent I : 1% 2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde solution in acetone.

Reagent II : 0.25% Ninhydrin in acetone.

Detection of amino acids on TLC plates :

Standard solutions (1 mg mL⁻¹) of amino acids were prepared in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ phosphate buffer (pH 8.0) and spotted on the TLC plates by means of a graduated mi-

cropipette (5 μL). The solutions were diluted further according to the required spot concentration. The dilution was made with the phosphate buffer. Plates were air-dried and subjected to TLC with *n*-propanol-water, 70 : 30 (v/v) as mobile phase. After development plates were dried and sprayed with reagent I.

The plates were dried in air and heated at 110 °C for 10 min in an oven. The plates were cooled and yellow color (Fig. 1) was noted (except in case of cysteine and cystine). Then the plates were sprayed with reagent II and colors were recorded after air drying (Table 1). Colors were further observed after heating the plates at 110 °C for 10 min. Colors were observed visually and the color pictures of chromatograms by digital camera were also recorded (Figs. 1 to 3). Detection limits for the amino acids after use of ninhydrin reagent alone is also given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Color of amino acids with reagent I in hot condition.

Fig. 2. Color of amino acids with ninhydrin in presence of reagent I in cold condition.

Fig. 3. Color of amino acids with ninhydrin in presence of reagent I in hot condition.

Table 1. Color formation of amino acids on TLC plates with reagent I-ninhydrin

Amino acids	Reagent-I + Ninhydrin				Detection limit of ninhydrin ^a (μg)	R _f values ^b
	Cold condition		Hot condition			
	Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)	Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)		
Glycine (1)	Orange with violet shade	0.80	Deep brown with violet shade	0.80	0.001	0.32
Alanine (2)	Deep brownish violet	0.80	Deep brownish violet	0.50	0.009	0.37
Valine (3)	Deep brownish violet	0.80	Deep brownish violet	0.30	0.010	0.45
Leucine (4)	Deep violet	0.80	Deep brownish violet	0.30	0.010	0.55
Isoleucine (5)	Deep violet	0.50	Deep brownish violet	0.30	0.200	0.53
Serine (6)	Yellowish brown with violet shade	0.80	Deep brownish violet	0.50	0.008	0.35
Threonine (7)	Yellowish brown with violet shade	0.10	Deep brown with violet shade	0.08	0.050	0.37
Aspartic acid (8)	Light violet	0.30	Light purple	0.10	0.100	0.33
Asparagine (9)	Yellowish brown	0.10	Yellowish brown	0.08	0.100	0.14
Glutamic acid (10)	Pinkish violet	0.05	Light brownish violet	0.01	0.040	0.35
Glutamine (11)	Yellowish pink with violet shade	0.08	Brownish violet	0.03	0.100	0.15
Lysine (12)	Brownish purple	0.30	Deep pinkish yellow	0.10	0.005	0.03
Histidine (13)	Yellowish purple	0.10	Yellowish pink	0.08	0.050	0.20
Arginine (14)	Violet	0.80	Pink	0.50	0.010	0.02
Phenylalanine (15)	Yellowish pink	0.80	Pink	0.50	0.050	0.58
Tyrosine (16)	Very light pink	0.80	Light pink	0.80	0.030	0.57
Tryptophan (17)	Reddish violet	0.50	Pink	0.10	0.050	0.62
Cysteine (18)	-	-	-	-	0.020	0.38
Cystine (19)	-	-	-	-	0.010	0.32
Methionine (20)	Violet	0.80	Pink	0.30	0.010	0.51
Proline (21)	Yellow	0.50	Yellowish-pink	0.30	0.100	0.26
Hydroxyproline (22)	Pink	0.30	Yellowish-pink	0.05	0.050	0.34

^aRef. Stahl (1969).

^b*n*-Propanol : water = 70 : 30 (v/v).

Limit of detection :

Limit of detection of amino acids were determined by spotting a standard solution (1 mg mL^{-1}) of the concerned amino acid on to the TLC plate, which was developed with mobile phase and spot was visualized using the reagent and ninhydrin as described in the above section. This process was repeated with successive dilution of the standard amino acids solutions until no detection was possible. The amount of amino acid just detectable was taken as detection limit.

Results and discussion

It is observed from Table 1 that ninhydrin gives various distinguishable colors with amino acids in the presence of spraying reagent (reagent I) before and after final heating. The color pictures of the chromatograms are reflected in the Figs. 1 to 3. The detection limits ($\mu\text{g spot}^{-1}$) are substantially low (0.01 to $0.80 \mu\text{g}$) which is quite comparable to ninhydrin alone. The detection limits before second heating are either equal or a little higher than those obtained after second heating. The reagent I alone produces yellow color with almost all the amino acids after heating. Color development is somewhat different almost in all the cases after second heating. Such color formations with high sensitivities of this modified spray reagent make it somewhat more useful than ninhydrin spray in the identification of amino acids on TLC plates.

The mechanism leading to such color formation is uncertain but a possibility is the formation of an 'imine' compound of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde with the amino acids which is probably responsible for the yellow color. This yellow color 'imine' then forms charge transfer (C-T)⁷ complex with ninhydrin (Scheme 1), colors of which are variable depending on the nature of the amino acids. On the other hand, the 'imine' intermediate may also undergo the reaction with ninhydrin in the following way (Scheme 1) to produce the complex A. Another possibility is the reaction of amino acids (unreacted or derived from 'imine' intermediate) with ninhydrin in the usual way to produce Ruhemann complex B (except for proline and hydroxyproline, Scheme 2). Since both complexes (A and B) are formed in unequal amounts depending on the nature of amino acids, we observed the variation of color contrast of the different amino acids².

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Conclusion

The newly introduced spray reagent (2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde) itself and also in combination with ninhydrin turns out to be very effective for identification of different amino acids by developing distinguishable colors on silica gel G TLC plates with high sensitivity.

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